

Titrimetric Determination of Certain Organic Compounds by Oxidation with Alkaline Potassium Permanganate

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A titrimetric procedure has been described for the determination of cinnamic, cyanoacetic, pyruvic and ascorbic acid, mannitol, thiourea and allylthiourea based on their oxidation at ordinary temperature with alkaline permanganate in presence of barium ions. In some cases nickel nitrate has been used as a catalyst. The effect of variation in the different factors influencing the stoichiometry of these oxidation reactions has also been investigated. The proposed method can be adopted for determining 0.01-0.1 M solution of these compounds with an accuracy of $\pm 0.8\%$ or better.

POTASSIUM permanganate is capable of oxidizing several organic compounds but the rate of oxidation is usually slow. This is a major problem in developing oxidimetric procedures for estimating organic compounds using permanganate as oxidant. The oxidation rate can be enhanced by heating the reaction mixture but then the autodecomposition of permanganate becomes quite appreciable and vitiates the accuracy of the method. According to Kolthoff¹, the oxidation of an organic substance proceeds more rapidly in alkaline medium than in acid. Imhof² achieved the complete oxidative breakdown of a number of organic compounds by utilizing oxidising power of permanganate both in alkaline and in acid solution but the time required for the completion of the reaction was 26 hrs.

The proposed procedure which requires only 15-30 mins for quantitative oxidation, is based on the following considerations. During the oxidation of organic compounds, in a fairly strong alkaline medium, permanganate gets reduced to manganate which is further reduced to manganese dioxide in the second step. This secondary reduction renders the oxidation reaction unsuitable for application in quantitative analysis. In presence of barium ions, the insoluble barium manganate is formed and hence the secondary reaction involving the formation of manganese dioxide scarcely proceeds at all³. On the basis of this fact a direct volumetric method has been evolved for determining certain organic compounds using alkaline permanganate at room temperature as oxidant. The time required for the completion of the reaction is shortened considerably when barium chloride is added to the reaction mixture⁴. Several sets of experiments were conducted to study the effect of change in the amount of sodium hydroxide, barium chloride, nickel nitrate and of the time on the stoichiometry of the oxidation of the organic substances tested. After

critically evaluating the results of these experiments, appropriate experimental conditions, leading to quantitative oxidation, were ascertained; these have been recorded in Table I.

Experimental

Sodium oxalate and potassium permanganate were of A.R. grade. 0.1 M permanganate solution was prepared and standardised with sodium oxalate⁵. Saturated solution of barium chloride was prepared from B.D.H. product. 0.25, 0.1 and 0.05% solutions of nickel nitrate and 10 M sodium hydroxide solution were prepared using E. Merck's variety. Since the solubility of cinnamic acid in water is poor, 0.1 M solution of its sodium salt was prepared and standardised by Imhof's method². 0.1 M cyanoacetic acid was prepared and standardised by alkalimetry. Pyruvic acid solution was also standardised by Imhof's method. Ascorbic acid solution was standardised by titration with potassium iodate solution in presence of potassium iodide and sulphuric acid⁶. Hypoiodite oxidation method was applied for standardising thiourea⁷.

In titrating an alkaline solution of permanganate with the solution of the organic substance to be determined, the difficulty is that if titration is done rapidly, more volume of reductant solution is required than required theoretically owing to incomplete reaction. On the other hand, if too much time is allowed during the titration, the volume of titrant is less than the stoichiometric value due to autodecomposition of permanganate. This difficulty has been circumvented by adopting the following procedure.

Procedure :

25 ml of 0.1 M potassium permanganate solution is pipetted into an Erlenmeyer flask and amounts of

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TABLE 1
(25.0 ml of 0.1 M POTASSIUM PERMANGANATE TAKEN FOR TITRATION)

Compound	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ added (ml)	10 M, NaOH added (ml)	Satd. BaCl ₂ added (ml)	Total titration time (mins)	No. of equiv. used per mole of reductant	Mg of substance 1 ml of 0.1 M KMnO ₄ soln
Cinnamic acid	2.6-2.8 (2.7 of 0.05%)	3-10 (5.0)	7-12 (8.0)	12-18 (15)	10	1.4815
Cyanoacetic acid	—	2-14 (5.0)	7-12 (8.0)	10-20 (15)	6	1.4176
Pyruvic acid	1.9-2.1 (2.0 of 0.05%)	4-8 (5.0)	6-10 (8.0)	15-20 (15)	10	0.8806
Ascorbic acid	1.5-1.8 (1.6 of 0.25%)	3-6 (4.0)	8-13 (10.0)	14-18 (15)	20	0.8806
Mannitol	2.6-3.0 (2.8 of 0.1%)	4-10 (5.0)	7-13 (10.0)	12-18 (15)	26	0.7007
Thiourea	—	3-8 (5.0)	7-12 (10.0)	15-22 (20)	12	0.6349
Allylthiourea	—	5-15 (10.0)	6-12 (10.0)	32-40 (35)	26	0.4468

Recommended volumes of nickel nitrate, sodium hydroxide and barium chloride solution are given in parentheses. When the volume of permanganate taken for titration is different from 25 ml, the volume of alkali, barium chloride and nickel nitrate solutions are changed proportionately.

TABLE 2

Compound	0.1 M permanganate used for titration (ml)	Solution used for titration (M)	Titre		% Error
			Theoretical	Obtained	
Cinnamic acid	25.0	0.05	5.0	5.0	Nil
	25.0	0.0166	15.0	15.1	-0.7
	25.0	0.0125	20.0	20.1	-0.5
Cyanoacetic acid	25.0	0.05	8.33	8.34	-0.1
	25.0	0.025	16.66	16.6	+0.4
	10.0	0.00925	26.66	26.8	-0.6
Pyruvic acid	50.0	0.1	5.00	4.96	+0.8
	25.0	0.025	10.00	10.03	-0.3
	25.0	0.0125	20.00	20.1	-0.5
Ascorbic acid	25.0	0.025	5.00	4.96	+0.8
	25.0	0.0125	10.00	10.00	Nil
	25.0	0.00625	20.00	20.2	-1.0
Mannitol	25.0	0.025	3.85	3.84	+0.3
	25.0	0.0125	7.69	7.70	-0.2
	25.0	0.00625	15.4	15.5	-0.7
Thiourea	50.0	0.1	4.17	4.19	-0.5
	25.0	0.025	8.33	8.34	-0.2
	25.0	0.0125	16.7	16.80	-0.7
Allylthiourea	25.0	0.025	3.85	3.86	-0.3
	25.0	0.0125	7.70	7.76	-0.8

Note: Microburette was used whenever titre was less than 10 ml.

sodium hydroxide, barium chloride and nickel nitrate as shown in Table 1 are added. The reaction mixture is heated to about 80° and titrated in 2-4 minutes with the sample solution to be determined. The approximate titre so obtained is noted. This hot titre is slightly less than the theoretical value because autodecomposition of permanganate increases with rise in temperature.

The same reaction mixture is taken and the volume of the titrant corresponding to the hot titre (as determined above) is added all at once. The mixture is kept for about 10-12 mins during which it should be frequently shaken. The titrant is then added dropwise slowly with thorough shaking till the permanganate colour disappears. The rate of addition of the titrant is so adjusted that in all

about 15 mins are required for the titration. In case of thiourea and allylthiourea the total titration time is 20 mins and 35 mins respectively. If the aforementioned mode of addition of the titrant is followed, the bulk of the reaction gets completed in the initial stage of the titration leaving very little permanganate for autodecomposition in the slow second stage of the titration. Thus, the autodecomposition of permanganate, a major source of error in these titrations, is kept at a minimum. Table 1 gives the range of quantities of nickel nitrate, sodium hydroxide and barium chloride to be added and titration time within which satisfactory results can be obtained.

Results and Discussion

The proposed procedure has been applied for

the determination of seven organic compounds. The analysis has been carried out at three concentration levels, using test solutions between the range 0.1 to 0.01 *M*. The recovery studies as presented in Table 2 show that the maximum error is $\pm 0.8\%$. Table 1 shows that the quantitative oxidation of the compounds tested can be achieved in 15-30 mins. In these redox reactions, permanganate is reduced to manganate involving only one electron change, hence its equivalent weight is equal to its molecular weight. This relationship coupled with the fact that large number of oxidizing equivalents are consumed per molecule of the compounds studied, makes the proposed method suitable for the quantitative analysis of dilute solutions of these substances.

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